

WORKSHOP

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR A
**MORE COMPETITIVE
NATIONAL AQUACULTURE**

Topics

Artificial intelligence
Functional feeds
Food safety
Animal welfare

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Dear Participant,

Welcome to the year 2035!

That's how far this Workshop is inviting you to go! In this exercise, we will explore the possible paths that national aquaculture may follow over the next decade, identifying threats, challenges, and opportunities along the way.

Imagine a scenario in which governments strongly prioritise decarbonisation, sustainability, investment in research and technological development, and the adoption of regenerative practices. What kind of future awaits us? Will we be entering an era of prosperity, with restored ecosystems and a more balanced economy? Could this context offer a genuine opportunity for positive global transformation within the aquaculture sector?

On the other hand, in a scenario marked by economic liberalism, reduced investment in research and technological development, and more flexible legislation on spatial planning and licensing, what impacts might we expect? And what advantages? Would the sector face the need for deep structural changes?

This is the challenge we put before you!

We aim to foster a critical and constructive reflection on the possible futures for national aquaculture. Together, we will identify the main barriers to its sustainable and competitive development, and co-create solutions that benefit all stakeholders along the seafood value chain.

We know the future is rarely black and white. But for the purposes of this exercise, that is exactly how we will approach it: two contrasting scenarios – one based on sustainability and technological innovation, the other on liberalisation and globalisation. Participants will be invited to analyse one of four key themes for the sector, exploring the challenges and opportunities in each of these alternative futures.

We look forward to your contribution to this exercise.

Your vision of the future of national aquaculture is essential!

Thank you.

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Content

Welcome note.....	2
Objectives.....	4
Reflection on the future of aquaculture.....	4
1 st scenario: A more sustainable and technological future.....	5
Scientific–technological investment and availability of alternative raw materials.....	5
Decarbonisation, acceptance, and diversification of products.....	6
Regulatory barriers and land use.....	6
Dependence on external sources and production costs.....	6
2 nd scenario: Economic liberalism.....	7
Scientific–technological investment and availability of alternative raw materials.....	7
Decarbonisation, acceptance, and diversification of products.....	8
Regulatory barriers and land use.....	8
Dependence on external sources and production costs.....	8
Session 1: Artificial intelligence.....	9
Session 2: Functional feeds.....	10
Session 3: Food safety.....	11
Session 4: Animal welfare.....	12

Objectives

The challenge we are proposing aims to gather input from a wide range of stakeholders across the aquaculture industry, in order to better understand current capabilities and difficulties, as well as how these may evolve in the future.

Starting from the current context and anticipating how national, European, and global developments might impact the sector, this initiative seeks to build a comprehensive vision and a solid foundation regarding the present state of national aquaculture. By bringing together diverse perspectives, the goal is not only to bridge gaps and overcome obstacles, but also to identify and seize both current and future opportunities.

This conversation is intended to have practical applications, informing various areas that regulate or support the sector. As a first step, a report will be produced summarising the premise, process, and outcomes of the session, and will be made available to all participants. Based on this report, two additional documents will be developed:

- A document addressed to regulatory bodies, outlining the main challenges faced by the sector and presenting proposals on how current regulations could be adjusted or upheld;
- A document addressed to funding and research entities, highlighting key challenges and gaps that can be addressed through new knowledge, setting priorities to guide investment in the research and development of national aquaculture.

To ensure the relevance and legitimacy of these documents, the list of participants will be included (with prior consent), acknowledging the collective contribution to this session. The perspectives presented will be attributed collectively, never individually, ensuring representation of both consensus and differing opinions.

Reflection on the future of aquaculture

While on the one hand the future of aquaculture will inevitably involve innovation and technological development aimed at animal welfare, the nutritional needs of the population, and contemporary principles of environmental sustainability, on the other hand, it is also clear that these advances will be shaped by various environmental, regulatory, and socio-economic barriers.

Taking these variables into account, from which different challenges, threats, and growth opportunities for the sector arise, it is possible to envision, over a time horizon of around ten years, two distinct future scenarios for the national aquaculture.

1st Scenario

A more sustainable and technological future

- Scientific and Technological Investment
- Availability of alternative raw materials
- Decarbonization
- Acceptance and diversification of products
- Regulatory barriers
- Territorial use
- Dependence on imports
- Production cost

Scientific-technological investment and availability of alternative raw materials

The strong encouragement of research focused on biotechnology and the development of new tools with an emphasis on sustainability is key. This includes innovative, efficient, and environmentally friendly extraction and fermentation methods. There is also growing support for the bioprospecting of alternative raw materials—such as insects, algae, terrestrial plants, marine invertebrates, and co-products from various productive sectors (e.g., agro-industrial). These efforts are part of a national strategy centred on the circular economy. Together, they enable the launch of new ingredients and additives with high nutritional and functional value onto the market.

Scientific research's investment in the development of tools, digital platforms, and automated, remotely operable, and minimally invasive equipment, fosters a more efficient, sustainable, real-time monitored, and intelligent aquaculture. The entry into the digital era not only improves connectivity between companies and sectors, but also enhances operational efficiency. This results in reduced production costs (e.g., unnecessary expenses on feed and use of resources), improved environmental sustainability (by minimizing waste and residues generated throughout the value chain), and more rigorous control of production conditions. Additionally, it enables the monitoring of water quality, processing, and distribution, as well as the early detection of diseases or stress factors that compromise the welfare and survival of the farmed animals. It also leads to a lower risk of contamination, ensuring that final products meet the highest standards of quality and food safety. In this context, the use of artificial intelligence (such as sensors, real-time monitoring systems, and digital platforms) becomes essential for decision-making related to the sector's operations.

Decarbonisation, acceptance, and diversification of products

The typical consumer is aware of the impact of their choices on health and on the preservation of the planet. The "One Health" concept is adopted, recognizing the interdependence between human, animal, and environmental health. Consumers mainly seek foods that are nutritious, healthy, safe, and of sustainable origin, regardless of the added cost. Barriers to the consumption of aquaculture products are beginning to decrease due to greater access to information and the implementation of promotional campaigns about the nutritional benefits associated with their consumption, as well as the use of technologies, feeds, and farming practices with a lower environmental footprint that also safeguard animal welfare.

The growing environmental awareness and preference for products certified for sustainability and food quality are encouraging the industry to invest in high-quality feeds and in the implementation of responsible farming practices, with a particular focus on animal welfare—even if this entails higher production costs. The commitment to integrated multitrophic systems, diversification of farmed species, reliable traceability tools and certification contributes to greater transparency and reinforces trust in the safety and quality of aquaculture products.

Regulatory barriers and land use

Policies encourage regenerative aquaculture practices, particularly through improved land and natural resource management, coastal zone protection, and the creation of legal instruments aimed at regulating, or even prohibiting, the use of certain chemical agents for pest and disease control. There is also a strong commitment to integrating aquaculture with agriculture, with the aim of optimizing resource use (e.g., using wastewater from aquatic systems for agricultural irrigation and fertilization, or repurposing co-products and waste across sectors), thereby contributing to the sustainability of food production industries.

The growing concern with climate change mitigation, environmental sustainability, animal welfare, and food safety is fostering a strict legislative framework regarding quality standards in animal production and the commercialization of safe and sustainable food for human consumption. Government efforts are directed toward preserving biodiversity and protecting certain areas, which limits land use and increases the challenges involved in obtaining licenses for agricultural and aquaculture production spaces.

Dependence on external sources and production costs

The implementation of circularity in the economy and the diversification of available raw materials promote a reduced dependence on foreign sources for feed production. This brings greater resilience to the national industry in situations of instability in global markets, such as those caused by armed conflicts that reduce the availability of essential raw materials for the sector. In this scenario, although cost increases are unavoidable, the risk of shortages is reduced. On the other hand, the need to comply with restrictive regulations, invest in technologies, and adopt more sustainable practices leads to an increase in production costs, resulting in more expensive food for consumers, which may cause a reduction in per capita fish consumption, especially among lower-income consumers.

2nd Scenario

Economic liberalism

- Scientific and Technological Investment
- Availability of alternative raw materials
- Decarbonization
- Acceptance and diversification of products
- Regulatory barriers
- Territorial use
- Dependence on imports
- Production cost

Scientific–technological investment and availability of alternative raw materials

The lack of investment in research leads to the technological stagnation of the industry. The responsibility for research falls mainly on the industry itself, making scientific advances less accessible to all actors in the sector. As a result, there is a drastic reduction in the introduction of alternative ingredients in feed production, leaving the potential of new products—aimed at improving fish health and welfare, as well as productivity and final quality—unexplored.

The growing demand for traditional feed ingredients leads to an increase in feed prices. Likewise, the development of prophylactic methods, antimicrobials, and welfare monitoring tools for aquaculture becomes heavily dependent on industry investment. The results of such research are mostly patented and commercially exploited by private companies, which raises the cost of their application and dissemination. This limitation in funding and/or lack of support for research and modernization may restrict the adoption of new technologies, including those based on Artificial Intelligence, thereby compromising the sector's effectiveness and responsiveness—particularly to new risks associated with global warming.

Without advanced technological resources, it becomes more difficult to ensure traceability, monitor product quality, and control diseases. Reduced production security resulting from these emerging risks undermines the sector's competitiveness, especially in international markets.

Decarbonisation, acceptance, and diversification of products

The loosening of regulations and the pursuit of greater economic competitiveness result in less emphasis on adopting sustainable measures, which are often costlier but essential for reducing environmental impact. This regulatory relaxation encourages the use of non-renewable energy sources, compromises animal welfare standards—due to greater freedom in the use of antibiotics to avoid significant production losses—and contributes to the stagnation of feed quality, a direct consequence of disinvestment in research. All these factors, combined with consumer scepticism and conservatism toward aquaculture products—driven by misinformation and the absence of promotional campaigns—lead to a decline in product acceptance and consumption, with a preference given to wild-caught products. This reduced acceptance, in turn, leads to a decrease in market value, affecting profit margins throughout the entire value chain. Consequently, this situation promotes disinvestment in the industry, making it more difficult to implement modernization measures.

Regulatory barriers and land use

With economic liberalization, national, and even European, legislation becomes more relaxed regarding aquaculture production. Reduced regulation of the sector allows for a greater focus on economic viability. Less environmental concern and lighter regulation increase the availability of sites for implementing aquaculture production units, which will be used by large economic groups to meet consumer demand for aquaculture products.

Dependence on external sources and production costs

With the removal of regulatory barriers, dependence on external sources increases, leading to a greater imbalance in the trade balance of fish and the ingredients used in feed production. Although on one hand there is greater freedom to use cheaper raw materials produced under lower quality standards, this also creates room for the entry of fish from countries with the capacity to produce at lower costs. As a result, the country becomes less resilient in situations of instability, such as international conflicts.

An ensuing economic recession would also make raw material prices more volatile, with direct repercussions on production costs. This instability may lead to an increased risk of contamination by undesirable substances, which could endanger the health and welfare of both farmed animals and fish consumers, negatively impacting the entire value chain.

Although production costs are reduced, profit margins cannot be high due to the need to compete with imported products. Environmental challenges, such as extreme events caused by climate change, may also reduce the resilience of production systems, with more frequent disease outbreaks—caused either by pathogens or by suboptimal temperature and other environmental conditions.

Session 1: Artificial intelligence

The need for sustainable and efficient aquaculture practices, without neglecting animal welfare and health, is becoming increasingly urgent. In this context, Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerges as a revolutionary and transformative tool across various dimensions of the aquaculture sector.

AI can be applied in multiple ways in aquaculture, from monitoring animal welfare to optimizing daily operations. Sensors and underwater cameras equipped with AI algorithms can monitor animal behaviour in real time, detecting signs of stress or disease before they become serious problems. This not only improves animal welfare but also increases productivity by reducing losses.

AI can also facilitate feed management by analysing growth and feeding behaviour data to automatically adjust the quantity and type of feed provided, minimizing waste and improving feed conversion. This results in more efficient and sustainable production with a smaller environmental footprint.

Forecasting environmental conditions is another area where AI can make a difference. The use of predictive models based on climate and oceanographic data—as well as toxic algal blooms and disease outbreaks—can help anticipate changes that may affect production, allowing aquaculture producers to take preventive measures. This is crucial in the context of climate change, where extreme events like heatwaves are becoming more frequent and intense.

Finally, AI can be an ally in traceability and food safety. Intelligent systems can monitor and record the entire life cycle of the animals, from production to distribution, ensuring transparency and consumer trust.

In this context, the participants in this working group will analyse the two practical scenarios with the aim of identifying the challenges and opportunities associated with the role of Artificial Intelligence in the aquaculture sector, with particular focus on animal welfare monitoring, feed optimization, environmental condition forecasting, and traceability. The workshop will conclude with a reflection on the next steps for implementing these solutions, reinforcing the importance of innovation and networked collaboration for the competitiveness of national aquaculture. What knowledge gaps still remain?

Session 2: Functional feeds

Aquaculture fish plays an increasingly important role in human nutrition, particularly within the Mediterranean diet, contributing to the supply of nutritious and healthy food in sufficient quantities and at more affordable prices for the population. However, the growth and productivity of this sector still face limitations related to sustainability, such as the heavy dependence on fishmeal and fish oil (obtained from wild species), especially in the formulation of feed for carnivorous species (e.g., gilthead seabream, European seabass, meagre), the high cost of feed production (resulting from the price and scarcity of raw materials), and the need to use pharmaceuticals (e.g., antibiotics, pesticides) that

may have potentially adverse effects on the farmed species, the environment, and fish consumers. In order to improve production practices and the sector's sustainability, research in aquaculture over recent decades has focused heavily on animal nutrition, particularly in the search for alternative ingredients that enhance the performance and growth of farmed species while also being environmentally and economically sustainable. Moreover, as with any other livestock production sector, the increasing need to farm fish under suboptimal conditions for growth and survival – due to worsening environmental contamination and the effects of climate change – has led to the development of “premium” feeds with functional properties aimed at improving the welfare and resilience of aquaculture species. In this context, contemporary research has explored various nutritional approaches, proposing the replacement of conventional raw materials with alternative protein and lipid sources (allegedly more affordable and sustainable, e.g., insects, co-products), as well as the supplementation of feeds with additives extracted from natural sources (e.g., micro- and macroalgae, yeasts) through biotechnology. Despite this ongoing “race” for new feed formulas and ingredients, several uncertainties still remain regarding the safety (for both animals and humans), sustainability (both environmental and economic), and acceptability (by the sector and by consumers) of these “eco-innovative” nutritional approaches.

In this context, the aim is for this working group to identify the main threats and challenges arising from the development and use of functional feeds in the aquaculture sector across both scenarios, and to discuss the opportunities—whether in terms of business potential, improvements in animal production practices, bioprospecting, or alignment with the objectives set out in the National Strategy for the Sea and the United Nations Sustainable Development Agenda. What knowledge gaps still remain?

Session 3: Food safety

Aquaculture plays an important role in food safety, as it must provide products that are safe and meet the nutritional needs of the human population. There is a negative, though contradictory, perception among consumers regarding farmed fish. On one hand, they recognize that aquaculture products are subject to greater control and traceability, which ensures high safety and quality standards; they are also more widely accepted in terms of sensory characteristics, more affordable, more readily available, and less affected by marine pollution, heavy metals, and parasites. On the other hand, consumers are concerned that aquaculture products may contain organic contaminants (e.g.,

polychlorinated biphenyls – PCBs, dioxins, and pesticides), antibiotics, and other pharmaceuticals. In recent years, the aquaculture sector has made significant efforts to replace animal-based ingredients (fishmeal and fish oil) with plant-based alternatives (e.g., cereals such as corn, wheat, and soy) in order to improve sustainability and profitability. However, this strategy may have negative implications for both consumer health and animal welfare, as cereals sometimes contain high levels of toxic fungal metabolites, such as mycotoxins (e.g., aflatoxin, ochratoxin A, fumonisin, deoxynivalenol).

It is important to recognize that many myths surround farmed fish. However, this method of fish production complies with a set of regulations and laws designed to ensure water quality, food safety, environmental protection, and public health. Europe requires member states to monitor contaminants in fish products and to implement HACCP plans within the industry in order to minimize risks to consumers and ensure that both producers and consumers have access to safer, high-quality, nutritious, and healthy products.

The global spread of digital tools has also enabled free access to useful platforms (e.g., FishChoice) that help consumers make informed decisions about fish consumption, providing information on nutritional benefits, potential risks, and sustainability.

This working group will identify and analyse the threats, challenges, and opportunities related to the food safety of aquaculture products based on the two previously identified scenarios. Specifically, the aim is to identify the main risks that may compromise the safety and quality of these products, to understand how that safety and quality can be ensured throughout the production and consumption chain, and to propose effective mitigation and adaptation strategies. What knowledge gaps still persist?

Session 4: Animal welfare

The context and the way aquaculture products are produced have a significant impact on the health and welfare of the animals. It is also well known that the quality of the final product—namely its nutritional value—is determined by the animal's overall health and welfare throughout the entire production process. In aquaculture, various factors contribute to the deterioration of animal health and/or welfare parameters. In a global warming scenario, the farming of aquatic animals is subject to unpredictable and often extreme temperature fluctuations. Changes in water temperature are a stress factor in themselves and are responsible for the proliferation of pathogenic agents that cause disease in animals already immunocompromised by stress. On the other hand, the production methods themselves prioritize process optimization focused on profit, inevitably leading to harm to the animals. High stocking densities, poor water quality, animal transport, and handling during vaccination are some of the inherent production factors, making it necessary to adopt additional measures to minimize their impact on the final product. Thus, ensuring good conditions and good practices in aquatic animal farming is in the interest of both the animal and the final consumer. In practice, such measures involve the implementation and use of innovative health and welfare monitoring tools that go beyond the simple observation of parameters. Fortunately, great strides have been made in the study and optimization of new non-invasive techniques for monitoring aquatic animal health, in the enrichment of their environments, and in the development of new vaccines and methods for their administration. Together, these represent prophylactic strategies that enhance the animal's robustness and welfare. These efforts foster more economically sustainable aquaculture, with fewer losses and less dependence on therapeutic drugs, which negatively affect the animal, the environment, and the final consumer. In parallel, production units benefit from improved training for producers and technicians in the use of these tools, which not only promote the specialization of the personnel involved but also ensure the effectiveness of their implementation. Finally, that same implementation should be subject to specialized oversight and regular audits by competent authorities.

In this context, this working group is expected to identify the main obstacles and challenges arising from the implementation of strategies that safeguard environmental health and animal welfare under both scenarios, and to discuss the opportunities. What knowledge gaps still remain? These are some of the key points that must be explored in order to create a more robust, ethical, and efficient production system.